

Quantum Security Mechanisms for Defense Applications

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Abstract. Many international organizations, such as the EU and NATO, and national governments have launched strategic initiatives supporting the migration to quantum-safe cryptography. Examples of such initiatives are Spanish CCN (Cybersecurity Defence of Spanish Cyberspace) endorsing post-quantum cryptographic algorithms like FrodoKEM and CRYSTALS-Kyber, and the European Union promoting secure quantum infrastructure through programs like Quantum Flagship, OpenQKD, and EuroQCI. Moreover, the efforts supported by the European Defence Fund reinforce the strategic importance of early quantum-resilient adoption across civil and defense sectors, through projects such as the Disruptive SDN secure communications for European Defence (DISCRETION) or the Quantum Agile and Resilient Military Communications (Q-ARM). This paper focuses particularly on defense-related quantum communication technologies, assessing not only quantum key distribution but also advanced primitives like quantum oblivious transfer, quantum digital signatures, and quantum secure direct communication, among others. It highlights their respective vulnerabilities, criticality, and potential countermeasures. Hybrid solutions that combine classical and quantum-

resistant encryption methods and cryptoagility are recommended to enhance resilience.

Keywords: Post-quantum cryptography, quantum key distribution, quantum oblivious transfer, quantum digital signatures, quantum secure direct communication.

1 Introduction

Quantum computing marks a transformative technological advancement, offering groundbreaking capabilities in many scientific areas such as molecular simulation and biology. However, it poses a serious threat to current cryptographic systems. A cryptographically relevant quantum computer, capable of running Shor’s and Grover’s algorithms, could break widely used encryption schemes like RSA (Rivest–Shamir–Adleman), elliptic curve cryptography, and Diffie–Hellman, potentially compromising global digital security. Though such machines are not yet realized, the risk is immediate due to the “Store Now, Decrypt Later” tactic, where adversaries collect encrypted data now to decrypt it later with future quantum capabilities. Mosca’s theorem [33] underscores the urgency of transitioning to quantum-safe cryptography before this threat materializes. To address this, both post-quantum cryptography (PQC) and quantum cryptography are under active development. PQC provides cryptographic solutions based on mathematical problems different from those used in conventional cryptography, these solutions being resistant to Shor’s algorithm. Quantum cryptography, on the other hand, provides mechanisms independent of mathematical formulations whose security depends on the basic principles of quantum mechanics.

Although many nations and international organizations, such as the National Security Agency in the USA and NATO, have advocated for the transition to post-quantum cryptography, it is crucial to acknowledge the limitations of the current PQC solutions. The new PQC algorithms, similarly to classical public-key cryptography algorithms, are not information-theoretically secure and rely on computational complexity assumptions for their security. Due to their recent development, the PQC algorithms are less well tested. The discovery of effective attacks against schemes such as Rainbow, GeMSS, and SIKE highlights the risks of relying on new methods that did not undergo sufficient scrutiny. These concerns are further heightened by the heavy reliance on a small set of hard computational problems, such as the Learning With Errors (LWE) problem and its variants (e.g., RLWE, PLWE), which form the foundation of major standards like ML-DSA (FIPS 204), SLH-DSA (FIPS 205) and ML-KEM (FIPS 203). A successful attack on these underlying computational complexity assumptions could undermine most of the current post-quantum migration efforts. For this reason, this paper also reviews additional quantum-based security primitives that could be of interest for securing military communications. However, also quantum-based security technologies, such as quantum key distribution (QKD), are not exempt from vulnerabilities in their implementation.

In this context, NATO, through its Science and Technology Organization (STO), is actively advancing research to integrate quantum communications into the military sphere. It has established three focused working groups: IST-217, dedicated to the development of a military-grade quantum Internet; IST-218, which examines multi-domain QKD for defense applications; and IST-219, which addresses the vulnerabilities inherent to quantum technologies. Specifically, this paper provides the initial outcomes of IST-219 regarding quantum primitives, such as QKD, Quantum Oblivious Transfer (QOT), Quantum Digital Signatures (QDS), Quantum Secret Sharing (QSS), Quantum Zero-Knowledge Proofs (QZKP), Multimodal Approaches (MA), and Quantum Secure Direct Communication (QSDC), highlighting their vulnerabilities and criticality.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section II provides an overview of the main QKD systems, covering their primary quantum state generation methods, corresponding protocols, and associated vulnerabilities - highlighting the most critical risks. Section III examines key quantum cryptographic primitives beyond QKD, focusing on the distinctions between purely quantum protocols and quantum-assisted (composite or hybrid) systems, along with their respective vulnerabilities and criticality. Particular attention is given to QKD implementations involving hardware components and the challenges they pose for formal security proofs. Finally, Section IV presents the paper's main conclusions.

2 Quantum key distribution overview

The aim of QKD is the generation of a completely random and secret cryptographic key shared between two legitimate parties. This key is intended for use in symmetric encryption algorithms. QKD protocols are said to be Information-Theoretic Secure (ITS) against both classical and quantum computational attacks due to their foundation on the laws of quantum mechanics [41]. In this section, we review the main encoding and protocols of QKD as well as their main vulnerabilities.

2.1 Protocols

Understanding QKD protocols begins with recognizing the different ways they can be categorized: (i) by physical implementation, (ii) by security assumptions, and (iii) by communication directionality. Physical implementation-based QKD protocols can be categorized as follows: (i) Discrete-Variable (DV) protocols use single photons with well-defined quantum states (e.g., polarization) (e.g. BB84 [6], B92 [5]); (ii) Continuous-Variable (CV) protocols utilize continuous attributes of light, such as phase and amplitude, allowing compatibility with standard telecom components (e.g. GG02 [21], No-switching protocol [26]); (iii) Entanglement-Based protocols rely on entangled photon pairs and Bell tests (e.g. E91 [11], BBM92 [7]); and (iv) Hybrid protocols combine elements of DV, CV, or entanglement with other techniques (e.g. based on Twin-Field QKD [53]).

Quantum protocols can also be categorized based on their security assumptions, often described using two parties: Alice (the sender) and Bob (the receiver). In the Prepare-and-Measure model, Alice prepares quantum states in specific bases and sends them to Bob, who measures the incoming states using appropriate detectors (e.g. BB84, B92). In the Entanglement-Based model, a central source distributes entangled particles to both Alice and Bob, who then perform independent measurements on their respective particles to obtain correlated outcomes (e.g. E91). The Measurement-Device-Independent model addresses vulnerabilities in measurement devices by having both Alice and Bob send their quantum states to a potentially untrusted third party, who performs a joint measurement. The protocol remains secure even if this third party or their equipment is compromised (e.g. MDI [53]). Regarding communication directionality, quantum protocols are categorized as follows: (i) Unidirectional, supporting only one-way quantum communication; and (ii) Bidirectional (Two-Way), allowing back-and-forth communication for tasks such as encoding or verification (e.g. Ping-Pong or LM05 Protocol [35]).

2.2 Vulnerabilities

While QKD offers theoretically unbreakable security grounded in the laws of quantum mechanics, practical implementations expose the system to various vulnerabilities stemming from adversarial strategies and device imperfections. A typical QKD protocol consists of a sequence of operations between two honest parties, Alice and Bob. It assumes prior authentication between those parties, for which different alternatives have been proposed, such as the use of Wegman-Carter-based authentication [1]. The aim of the communication is to achieve: i) *Correctness* of the keys generated by Alice and Bob (the keys must be identical), and ii) *Secrecy* of the keys since only Alice and Bob should have any knowledge of the generated key. However, QKD has to face vulnerabilities in its implementation as reported in [8].

In classical systems, eavesdropping is undetectable by design. However, in quantum communication, any interaction with the quantum channel by an eavesdropper (Eve) introduces detectable disturbances. These disturbances typically appear as increased error rates at the receiver, signaling potential eavesdropping attempts. Nonetheless, advanced attacks may be harder to detect, especially if Eve has access to quantum memory and sophisticated measurement strategies.

Attacks on QKD systems are typically categorized into three classes. In *individual attacks*, Eve interacts with each quantum signal separately, attaching an ancilla and measuring each one independently. Examples include intercept-resend and beam-splitting attacks. *Collective attacks* follow a similar interaction model, but Eve postpones her measurements to perform a joint measurement over all collected ancillae, allowing for greater information extraction.

The most general and powerful class is *coherent attacks*. In this case, Eve entangles all transmitted signals with a global ancilla and performs a global joint measurement. These attacks exploit the full power of quantum mechanics and are limited only by fundamental physical principles. Although theoretically

detectable, they present a significant threat if the protocol or devices are not properly designed, since their detectability could be reduced.

Beyond theoretical attacks, real-world vulnerabilities arise from device imperfections and side channels. Practical issues include detector blinding attacks, multi-photon emissions from imperfect sources (leading to photon number splitting), and miscalibrations [8]. These flaws can be exploited unless specifically addressed in the protocol.

To mitigate such vulnerabilities, newer protocols like Measurement-Device-Independent QKD (MDI-QKD) have been proposed. MDI-QKD neutralizes detection side attacks typically focused on the detectors by having both Alice and Bob send quantum states to a third-party measurement device, whose trustworthiness is not required. This significantly enhances practical security without sacrificing the benefits of QKD.

3 Quantum Cryptographic Primitives beyond QKD

While QKD remains a cornerstone for securely sharing symmetric keys through quantum mechanics, e.g., [6, 11, 53], there are other quantum cryptographic primitives beyond QKD that hold significant promise for defense applications. Moreover, quantum cryptography still faces numerous challenges, including resistance to physical attacks, enabling autonomous authentication, managing hybrid keys, and certifying devices. As a result, exploring and developing quantum cryptographic primitives beyond QKD is critical to addressing these emerging needs.

3.1 Quantum Oblivious Transfer (QOT)

Oblivious Transfer (OT) primitive, especially the 1-out-of-2 variant [52], plays a foundational role in secure multiparty computation, enabling a sender to share one of two messages without knowing which was received [37]. Classical OT relies on public-key cryptography, which becomes insecure in the quantum era due to its dependence on problems like factorization and discrete logarithms.

QOT addresses these limitations. In the standard protocol, Alice encodes bits in photon polarization using random bases; Bob, unaware of the basis, can only partially retrieve information unless he waits to measure after Alice reveals the bases—an action that breaks the protocol if he has a quantum memory. This vulnerability is mitigated under the noisy-storage model, which assumes adversaries cannot store quantum data reliably for long.

Recent advances introduced oblivious keys, enabling a two-phase QOT, consisting of oblivious key distribution phase and oblivious transfer phase [38]. This framework uses hash-based commitments, secure even against quantum adversaries, based on the difficulty of finding collisions across thousands of hash functions in milliseconds. Furthermore, new protocols have been proposed that achieve simulation security in the plain model against malicious quantum polynomial-time adversaries, using one-way functions and quantum-enhanced commitment schemes.

3.2 Quantum Digital Signature (QDS)

Digital signatures ensure message integrity, authenticity, and non-repudiation. Widely used in modern communication, they are typically based on asymmetric cryptographic algorithms like RSA, Diffie-Hellman, or elliptic curves. However, these schemes are vulnerable to quantum attacks using Shor’s algorithm. To counter this, PQC algorithms have emerged, notably through the NIST competition [42], which has already resulted in two signature standards: FIPS 204 [43] and FIPS 205 [44]. Simultaneously, quantum cryptography is exploring signature protocols whose security stems from quantum mechanics, akin to QKD.

Several QDS protocols have been proposed over the years. In 2001, the first QDS scheme [19], based on Lamport’s one-way function, was proven to be information-theoretically secure, but it requires long-term quantum memories, making it impractical for current use. In 2014, a QDS protocol [10] was introduced that eliminated the need for quantum memories but relied on secure quantum channels and was vulnerable to coherent forging attacks. A 2016 scheme [3] improved upon this by utilizing secure classical channels through a symmetrization step, removing the need for secure quantum channels, though it limited message length and scalability. In 2021, an enhancement was made by eliminating the symmetrization step, improving efficiency, but the protocol remained restricted to signing short messages [32].

Additionally, Quantum-Assisted Digital Signatures (Q-DS) combine QKD-generated keys with classical cryptographic primitives. In 2023, a Q-DS protocol [17] was proposed that uses QKD-generated symmetric keys along with NIST-recommended hash functions and XOFs, enabling arbitrary-length messages and offering efficiency comparable to post-quantum cryptography (PQC). However, this scheme is limited to a single signer and two verifiers. In 2024, a refinement of this protocol [46] replaced hash functions with WC-MACs, while maintaining the same verifier limitations.

3.3 Quantum Secret Sharing (QSS)

Secret sharing is a cryptographic technique that splits a secret into multiple shares, requiring a threshold number t of them (in a (t, n) -scheme) to reconstruct the secret. Classical schemes like Shamir’s and Blakley’s [40] guarantee information-theoretic security using polynomial interpolation, assuming private channels—often established via QKD—exist between dealer and shareholders.

QSS aims to generate and share secrets using quantum properties such as multipartite entanglement. Most QSS schemes are (n, n) -threshold schemes where all participants must cooperate. The pioneering protocol by Hillery et al. [23] used GHZ states but was inefficient and insecure against internal adversaries [36].

Subsequent advances introduced measurement-device-independent setups [15] and graph states [4], improving protocols’ robustness against photon loss and adversarial attacks. These protocols enable applications such as *Quantum Conference Key Agreement* (QCKA), though QSS generally leaks more error-correction

information than QCKA. For a quantum bit error rate (QBER) q , QCKA requires $h(q)$ bits of correction, while QSS requires $h(Q)$, with $Q > q$ under most conditions due to noise in GHZ-based XOR operations.

Until recently, many QSS protocols lacked full security proofs, especially against dishonest insiders. This gap was addressed by Adesso et al. [25] and Walk et al. [49], who respectively provided composable security for continuous- and discrete-variable QSS, including finite-key effects. Their results show that entanglement-based QSS can outperform classical QKD-based sharing in constrained quantum networks.

To enhance practicality, newer QSS schemes avoid multipartite entanglement. A notable example is a $(2, 2)$ -threshold scheme based on Bell pairs [51], proven secure against both eavesdroppers and malicious users. However, it is limited in scalability and range. Another innovation by Chen et al. [22] uses a twin-field QKD approach to enable QSS over distances beyond 200 km, though with less general insider security.

Alternative protocols eliminate entanglement entirely by employing *sequential operations* on a single quantum system [47, 31]. These trade off entanglement distribution with challenges in routing and implementing random unitaries. One such protocol, by Qi et al. [20], achieves (n, n) -QSS via coherent-state injection and homodyne detection, requiring a shared phase reference and specific channel configurations.

Finally, Liu et al. [28] propose a practical QSS scheme that removes the need for phase-locking between participants. The dealer sends multiplexed coherent signals across parallel shareholder chains, who independently encode information. After traversing all paths, the dealer demultiplexes and detects the signals to extract shared keys. The setup enables scalable networks and supports classical secret sharing on top of parallel QKD channels.

3.4 Quantum Zero-Knowledge Proof (QZKP)

Zero-Knowledge Proofs (ZKPs) are cryptographic protocols enabling a prover to convince a verifier of knowledge without revealing the actual information. Introduced by Goldwasser, Micali, and Rackoff in 1985 [18], valid ZKPs must satisfy completeness, soundness, and zero-knowledge properties. ZKPs are divided into interactive, e.g., Fiat-Shamir [14], and non-interactive types like zk-SNARKs [39] and zk-STARKs [27], the latter being more scalable and avoiding trusted setups.

ZKPs have wide applications: authentication (with or without pre-shared secrets), privacy-preserving blockchain transactions (e.g., Zcash), anonymous payments, secure signatures, access control, and secure multi-party computation. However, many classical ZKPs depend on cryptographic assumptions (e.g., RSA, ECC) that are vulnerable to quantum algorithms like Shor's.

Post-quantum alternatives, such as lattice-based schemes (e.g., NTRU), zk-STARKs, or isogeny-based cryptography, offer quantum-resistant zero-knowledge protocols. Moreover, Quantum Zero-Knowledge Proofs (QZKPs) leverage quantum mechanics to ensure security beyond computational assumptions. For example, a QZKP authentication scheme using pre-shared secrets and key-derivation

functions has been proposed in [16]. The protocol includes: (1) synchronization and key derivation; (2) transmission of quantum states encoded by that key; and (3) verification through QBER estimation. If QBER is within the threshold, authentication succeeds.

These quantum and post-quantum ZKP systems represent vital developments in building secure, future-proof authentication and privacy-preserving systems.

3.5 Multimodal Approaches (MA)

Multimodal solutions combine QKD with other cryptographic methods, such as post-quantum and traditional asymmetric cryptography, to provide layered security. This hybrid approach enhances resilience by leveraging the complementary strengths of different techniques.

A notable implementation is the Multimodal Key Establishment System (KES) by evolutionQ, which derives encryption keys from multiple cryptographic primitives. This approach offers several benefits, including strong computational security, as multiple layers provide backup protection in case one method fails. It also ensures forward secrecy, meaning past communications remain secure even if keys are compromised in the future. Additionally, the system provides post-compromise security, protecting future data after a compromise occurs. Furthermore, it offers identity theft protection, defending against impersonation even if the underlying infrastructure is breached.

Multimodal KES works with existing infrastructure and supports gradual integration of QKD. Keys are derived from two input shares: one from a quantum-safe authenticated key exchange (AKE) combining classical and post-quantum AKE, and another from an out-of-band secure channel.

The system includes Key Distribution Hubs (KDHs) and Multimodal Agents (MAs) installed at endpoints (e.g., Alice, Bob). MAs register with a KDH to retrieve and store pre-key data, enabling key derivation even without an active network connection. These pre-keys allow MAs to establish long-term, quantum-resistant keys.

A Multimodal KES includes two core components: a lightweight MA, deployed at endpoints or within applications, and a Key Distribution Network with at least one KDH. Registered MAs can establish secure keys with peers, made available through standard interfaces like ETSI GS QKD 014 [12], QKD 004 [13], KMIP [34], or SKIP [24].

3.6 Quantum Secure Direct Communication (QSDC)

QSDC is an innovative communication protocol that enables direct transmission of confidential information by exploiting fundamental quantum principles. Unlike traditional cryptographic approaches or QKD, QSDC transmits information without requiring prior key distribution, streamlining communication and enhancing security. It also provides unconditional security, leveraging quantum

mechanics to detect any eavesdropping attempts. Additionally, the use of quantum entanglement and superposition enhances the system’s robustness against interception by utilizing strongly correlated quantum states.

Compared to QKD, which separates key distribution from message transmission, QSDC directly encodes the message into quantum states. This reduces the complexity and potential points of failure in communication. QSDC and QKD both use quantum channels (e.g., fiber optics, free-space, satellite), but QSDC is particularly suitable for real-time, secure messaging. Although QSDC is still under development, it holds high potential for future secure communication systems, offering unmatched efficiency and resistance to quantum threats.

Various QSDC protocols exist, including: i) Ping-Pong Protocol [2], ii) Decoy State Protocol [29], iii) Quantum Relay Protocol [45], iv) Four-Party Protocol [48], v) Quantum Cryptographic Authentication Protocol [50], vi) MDI-QSDC [9] and vii) Quantum Repeater-Based QSDC [30]. These protocols differ in assumptions, functioning, security parameters, and vulnerabilities. The Ping-Pong Protocol is one of the earliest QSDC schemes, based on the use of entangled qubits sent back and forth between sender and receiver. While simple and intuitive, it is vulnerable to intercept-resend and denial-of-service attacks without additional safeguards. The Decoy State Protocol enhances QSDC security by introducing randomly inserted decoy photons to detect eavesdropping attempts, improving resistance against photon-number-splitting attacks. The Quantum Relay Protocol uses intermediate trusted nodes to extend communication range and detect interference, though it depends on node trustworthiness. The Four-Party Protocol adds a control center and an authenticator to manage and verify communications, enabling more secure and authenticated message exchange in multi-user environments. The Quantum Cryptographic Authentication Protocol integrates classical authentication with quantum transmission to ensure message origin and integrity, addressing identity verification along with confidentiality. The Measurement-Device-Independent QSDC (MDI-QSDC) removes vulnerabilities from measurement devices—often the weakest link in quantum systems—by letting an untrusted third party perform measurements without compromising security. Finally, the Quantum Repeater-Based QSDC introduces quantum repeaters to overcome distance limitations, allowing entanglement distribution and secure communication across long distances while maintaining high fidelity.

3.7 Vulnerabilities

Quantum systems face a range of vulnerabilities that can compromise their security. Imperfections in quantum devices, such as photon sources and detectors, can lead to weak entanglement, photon loss, or inaccuracies in measurements, which can weaken the system’s reliability. Noise and decoherence in the quantum channel can distort signals and reduce the effectiveness of security protocols. In addition, eavesdropping attacks are a significant threat, with adversaries potentially intercepting photons without disturbing the system enough to trigger detection mechanisms. Sophisticated attacks, like photon-number-splitting or

intercept-and-resend strategies, may allow an attacker to bypass security without detection. Other vulnerabilities include the risk of compromised relay stations or untrusted devices within the quantum network, which could manipulate data or introduce errors, undermining the integrity of the communication. These challenges highlight the ongoing need to enhance the robustness and resilience of quantum communication systems.

To mitigate vulnerabilities in quantum communication, techniques like entanglement purification, error correction, and regular calibration of photon sources and detectors can improve entanglement quality and reduce photon loss. To address photon-number-splitting attacks, using stronger decoy states and enhancing detection systems can help. Preventing relay manipulation involves implementing trust verification protocols and regular checks for errors in entanglement swapping. Reducing channel loss through better infrastructure and error correction, along with secure encryption of relay channels, also strengthens security. Overall, improving the robustness of entanglement swapping and ensuring the reliability of quantum communication channels are essential for secure communication.

Photon loss and detector imperfections are significant challenges in quantum communication, but the disturbance caused by eavesdropping remains a key advantage, as it enables detection of interception attempts. By using high-quality photon sources and robust detection methods, these vulnerabilities can be minimized, ensuring secure communication. Photon-number-splitting attacks pose a threat in the Decoy State Protocol, but improvements in detection techniques and protocol designs can mitigate this issue. The protocol is generally secure when properly implemented. Channel loss and relay manipulation are moderate concerns, which can be addressed through effective relay station management and error correction strategies. Overall, the severity of vulnerabilities is moderate, and risks can be controlled through careful monitoring and prevention of malicious behavior.

4 Conclusions and future directions

Quantum technologies are expected to significantly enhance secure military communications, offering strong protection against both classical and quantum-era threats. However, the integration of these technologies, especially those involving cryptographic primitives beyond standard QKD, requires rigorous security evaluation. This includes, in particular, emerging quantum-assisted and hybrid schemes, which often present new vulnerabilities related to hardware, protocol design, and unproven security assumptions. As NATO and allied forces move toward high quantum technology readiness, it is critical to anticipate adversarial exploitation and ensure that only thoroughly vetted systems are deployed. In this context, maintaining a well-defined and regularly updated list of secure, quantum-safe cryptographic schemes is essential to guide development, standardization, and operational use. Comprehensive vulnerability assessments and countermeasure strategies must be in place before these systems are introduced

into mission-critical environments. In this regard, there are multiple ongoing activities at the defense level that aim to design, identify, develop, and implement quantum-safe solutions for military use cases. These activities take place within the collaboration frameworks provided by NATO STO activities, European Defence Program, and military national programs, such as the COINCIDENTE program from the Spanish government.

Quantum security mechanisms represent a transformative opportunity for enhancing the protection of sensitive information and communication in defense environments. Protocols such as quantum key distribution, quantum digital signatures, quantum secure direct communication, and other quantum cryptographic primitives offer the potential for information-theoretic security, making them highly attractive for high-assurance military applications. These tools can augment or even replace classical cryptographic systems in scenarios where resilience against advanced adversaries, including those with quantum capabilities, is essential.

Nevertheless, practical challenges persist. Issues such as photon loss, channel noise, hardware imperfections, and the limited maturity of device-independent quantum protocols must be addressed before widespread operational deployment. Additionally, the future impact of quantum computing on post-quantum cryptography highlights the need for layered and adaptable security architectures that integrate both quantum and classical techniques.

Importantly, the increasing complexity of modern military multi-domain operations (MDO) — spanning land, air, sea, space, and cyberspace — demands multi-domain quantum security solutions. Secure and interoperable communications across these domains require cryptographic mechanisms that can function robustly in diverse and contested environments. Quantum-secured networks, supported by technologies like Multi-Domain QKD and trusted relay architectures, can be essential for achieving mission assurance and strategic advantage in this context.

To prepare for this paradigm shift, continued investment in research, standardization, and experimentation under real-world conditions is crucial. NATO's ongoing initiatives, along with national defense programs, reflect a growing recognition that quantum technologies will play a pivotal role in securing MDO in the decades to come.

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